

A proposed strategy to promote family reform in light of contemporary developments

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Abstract

The issue of family education is one of the most pressing issues in the political and social life of the contemporary world. Human societies have found in family education a starting point for reforming their conditions and enhancing their capabilities. Every time the alarm bell rings, these societies mobilize their educational systems to reform in order to confront the danger and build the human being capable of overcoming the trials of civilization and participating in its construction. Family reform is humanity's salvation from the crises and successive tribulations it is suffering from today, which have led strong individuals to assault their weaker siblings, violating sanctities as much as they can reach and exploiting their strength. The contemporary family reform system encompasses all human aspects of society, making it suitable for all who desire to live a good life. The study aims to achieve family reform through proper selection of both spouses and proper upbringing of children in all its forms.

Keywords

family reform , contemporary , developments , societies , education

Introduction:

The greatest reform for contemporary society is family reform. Therefore, the family reform strategy addresses human nature, strikes a balance between the spirit and the body, and does not neglect the temporal circumstances and conditions that govern it. It is clear to any rational observer of contemporary reality that family reform is the foundation of contemporary reform.

The contemporary reform system encompasses all human aspects of society, making it suitable for all who desire to live a good life.

There is no doubt that the various social and educational institutions in society, and the family in particular, acquire great importance in relation to essential and sensitive issues concerning the members of society, such as the issues of youth delinquency, because they are responsible for raising the human being and

preparing him to practice his various social roles and functions in life in accordance with the requirements of society and reality (Karim, 2008, 231).

Family education issues include all aspects of education from choosing and raising children and family cohesion and so on, raising parents' awareness of children's rights, the danger of domestic violence, moral education by instilling good values such as honesty, trustworthiness, being kind to parents and having good morals, family education includes relationships between spouses and treating family problems such as divorce, khul', adultery and inheritance....., and this is what the current study seeks, because any defect in any aspect of family education has a harmful effect on the individual and society.

Study Problem:

The absence of proper family upbringing and education in the formation of the individual leads to changes in their behavior and actions. Their behavior and actions are determined by their upbringing in the society in which they live. The most important thing that connects them to society is the social relationships between them and groups and individuals in the local and wider community. Furthermore, the responsibility for regulating society's youth falls entirely on the family. It is no secret to anyone who is perceptive that society suffers from numerous forms of deviance, indicating serious family corruption. Family corruption begins with domestic violence and leads to numerous social problems, including high rates of divorce among married couples, high rates of spinsterhood and reluctance to marry among both men and women, high rates of theft, the prevalence of murder, both self-inflicted and other murders, and the spread of drugs and alcohol. Added to this is the widespread prevalence of the internet and websites that corrupt morals, as well as the prevalence of cybercrimes, which makes the study of family reform increasingly difficult.

The study's problem can be summarized in the following main question:

What is the proposed strategy for promoting family reform in light of contemporary developments and its impact on the individual and society?

The following questions branch out from this question:

1. What is the importance of family reform in some family education issues?
What family issues can a contemporary educational reform approach address?
2. What are the effects of contemporary family reform on the individual and society?
3. How can contemporary family reform be promoted?

Study Objectives:

The current study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- Define the importance of family reform and its impact on the individual and contemporary society.
- Clarify family issues and their reform through a contemporary reform approach.
- Explain the effects of family reform on the individual and society, highlighting the educational benefits of the reform approach.
- Strengthen the contemporary reform approach to achieve comprehensive, integrated reform of all aspects of the family.

Significance of the Study:

This study is particularly important as we live today in a world of divergent and divergent educational cultures, which differ on some issues related to the family.

- It is hoped to develop an educational curriculum for some contemporary educational ideas and guidelines.
- The study will help solve some of the family problems facing individuals and society.
- It is expected to assist educational institutions of all kinds in carrying out their educational functions with steady and clear steps, free from confusion and randomness.
- Building the individual's character in all aspects of Islamic education, such as faith, morality, and social aspects.
- Highlighting the role of family reform in establishing the foundations and principles of contemporary education, characterized by soundness, stability, discipline, flexibility, continuity, and other educational characteristics.
- Deriving legitimate educational solutions that protect the nation from the evils of family deviations and address their dangers and negative effects on the nation's reality and future.

Study Methodology:

The nature of this research requires a descriptive approach. With its tools and methods, it is the most appropriate method for the study. It does not stop at describing the phenomenon—the subject of the study—but rather extends to analysis, interpretation, and comparison to arrive at meaningful generalizations that expand information about the phenomenon, thereby increasing insight into the phenomenon (Al-Qadir, 2006, 58). Based on this, the researcher explores family reform.

Study Terminology:

Family Reform in Practice: Family reform aims to educate individuals, improve their condition and the conditions of those around them, and reform the family, including the upbringing of children. A sound family is the foundation of reform that regulates people's lives, stabilizes their affairs, and strives to improve their conditions as a whole. It also encompasses all aspects of human behavior and activities at the individual, family, and contemporary society levels.

Modern Developments:

Procedural Developments: New issues that did not exist before and require ijtiḥād (independent reasoning) to determine their rulings, so that family reform takes into account these emerging issues of this era.

Study Limits:

Substantive Limits: Family reform.

Temporary Limits: From 2022 to 2024.

Spatial Limits: Faculty of Education, Arish University.

Previous studies:

A study by Ali Abdul Mohsen Braisem Albu Muhammad (2011) entitled: The Role of Family Education in Shaping Children's Social Values. The study presented the following suggestions: Spreading educational awareness among parents through the media, enlightening them about the dimensions of a democratic or assertive parenting style, highlighting the positive outcomes that impact children's psychological, social, and academic lives, and clarifying the negative effects of poor parenting styles and the negative role parents can play in this.

- Parents should pay attention to their children's friendships, given the importance of friendship groups in the socialization process. They should also direct children's activities and participation toward peer groups, which reinforces their values and attitudes.

- social institutions should participate in the educational process through media and other channels, providing religious or social discourse that focuses on the values and ideals embodied by the prophets and imams.

A study by Salem Salama Anaswa (2011) entitled: The Role of Family and School in Shaping a Child's Personality.

The study concluded that:

- The necessity of beginning Quranic learning as soon as the young child is mentally and physically prepared for instruction, as advocated by comprehensive Islamic education.
- Gradual learning during the teaching process without rushing the process, taking into account individual differences, studying the child's psychology, instilling scientific thinking in the student regarding the steps taken and practical application of what is taught, stimulating activity, and creating a healthy environment through sound work.
- Adopting the principle of flexibility between teacher and learner during the teaching process so that the child gains the ability to benefit from knowledge.
- Taking care of the child's health and nutrition.
- Focusing on positive habits from an early age to prevent negative habits from infiltrating Muslim children, as stipulated by modern education.

A study by Muhammad al-Nasr Hassan (2014) entitled: *The Role of Education in Confronting Moral Corruption in Society*.

This study revealed several findings, the most important of which are:

- Corruption leads to a decline in the application of social justice as a result of the concentration of wealth and power in the hands of a small group, the unequal distribution of income and loans, and the absence of social and economic equality.

One of the factors contributing to corruption is that certain social customs and traditions play a role in the growth of this phenomenon or in its uprooting.

The phenomenon of corruption has deep roots embedded within the structure of our society, is highly visible and widespread, and receives support and backing.

Study by Nariman Muhammad Ali Mustafa (2014), entitled: *"Social Deviance and Ways to Address It in Contemporary Education."*

The study concluded that:

There are multiple causes of deviant behavior, with an emphasis on two primary factors in the emergence of this socially unacceptable behavior: heredity and environment.

Confronting social deviance requires instilling Islamic morals and developing spiritual education by shaping the Muslim's character and morals through socialization institutions. This helps achieve immunity against all forms of deviation. Only morality can achieve this confrontation.

A study by Safaa Ahmed Mohamed Ali (2017) titled: Parental Styles as Perceived by Children and Their Relationship to Psychological Adjustment: A Study of Secondary School Students in Khartoum State (Karari Locality). The study concluded that: Positive parental styles are high, while negative parental styles are low. There are also statistically significant differences in the degree of parental styles according to the gender of the student (male, female). Furthermore, there is a correlation between parental styles and the educational level (of the mother and father). There are no statistically significant differences in the parental styles of .(fathers and mothers according to the variable of school type (typical, geographical

First: Contemporary Issues of Family Reform:

Society has been concerned with reforming the individual, the family, and society through family reform. This was evident when it spoke of marriage and promoted it as the legitimate path that protects society from moral deviation, preserves children and their rights to choose, breastfeed, and raise them, regulates marital relations between men and women, and fully regulates family relations. It also works to ensure that married life remains based on love, understanding, affection, and compassion, and the rights and duties that arise from this relationship, all of which aim to reform and preserve the cohesion of society.

The greatest aspect of reform on earth is the reform of the family, as the family is considered the first basic unit of social construction. It is the starting point for

growth, experience and success for the individual. In its reform lies the reform of society. The family plays the primary role in building the edifice of any society, by strengthening its unity and cohesion and regulating the behaviour of its members, in a manner that is compatible with the different social roles of each of them (Haqqi and Abu Sakina, 2018, 9). Reform includes many basic pillars, including the following:

1. Choosing the Right Wife and Husband:

Choosing a mother or father is one of the most difficult matters in light of modern developments and the overwhelming number of temptations and means of corrupting marital life. This has led to high divorce rates among newlyweds, family dissolution, the loss of children, and the loss of the nation's present and future. Therefore, choosing a wife based on religion has become an urgent necessity, advocated by all, to reduce family problems and violence within the family, the harm of which affects society as a whole.

A. Choosing a Wife:

A man must make a good choice of the mother of his child. He should choose a righteous wife who will provide the ideal upbringing for his children. A wife is a source of comfort and protection for the husband. She is his life partner, his homemaker, the mother of his children, the center of his heart, and the repository of his secrets and private conversations. She is the most important pillar of the family. She is the mother who gives birth to children, and in her arms the child's emotions are formed, his talents are nurtured, he learns his language, acquires many of his traditions and customs, learns his religion, and becomes accustomed to social behavior (Blasi, 1999, 71).

On this basis, a wise man must choose the mother. One of the latest developments in today's age is choosing based on beauty, lineage, or wealth, far removed from religion. This is one of the reasons for the high rate of divorce, and it brings misery to oneself and a great deal of enmity to one's society.

B - Choosing a Spouse:

Education has stressed the importance of a good husband, so that they should look for a suitor who is religious and moral, so that he can fulfill his duty in taking care of the family, fulfilling marital rights, raising children, and being a proper guardian in being jealous for honor and securing the needs of the home through giving and spending (Alwan, 2013, 31). A good father is a model and example for his children in raising them, and it is easy for the children to imitate their father in good behavior in his life, because not choosing based on morals and religion makes the girl fall into the care of a man who does not know the rights of the wife, and does not protect her honor, but rather it reaches the point of sacrificing her honor for money, as happens on YouTube, Facebook, and others.

2. Factors of Contemporary Family Stability:

Family stability is one of the greatest and most sublime goals of education, as it is the nucleus of society and upon which its stability depends. This results in good social interaction, which is the greatest cause of family stability, especially in our contemporary era. It provides family members with security and peace of mind, and protects children from deviance, homelessness, and crime.

The family is the most important and greatest institution in the world, as it is the building block of society. No civilization can exist without family cohesion, nor can any other institution in existence fulfill the important role it plays (Arcovi, 2009, 143). Family stability includes the following:

A - Constructive cooperation between spouses:

A cohesive family, pervaded by an atmosphere of love and harmony, raises its children in a state of psychological stability, free from the misery of life and the unhappiness of disagreement and discord. A good example is an upbringing in which the innate and rational aspects are integrated, supported by the divine approach. Upbringing is based on adherence to religious principles, and religious teachings permeate the family environment through the good role models of the father and mother. This is where upbringing is at its best, as faith in God opens vast horizons for love, giving, mercy, tolerance, and altruism in the souls of children, in an atmosphere filled with deep emotional warmth (Al-Mansi, 2006, 441).

B - Satisfying the Sexual Instinct:

This instinct is described as innate because it is inherent and inseparable from the human soul. God Almighty has made a man's need for a woman similar to a woman's need for a man, likening this need to clothing. By meeting under one garment, they become like one body. What drove them to this clothing was the satisfaction of their individual instincts. This precise expression describes this innate instinct. This relationship is based on love and each party's fulfillment of the other's desires, along with the preliminaries of sexual relations between them, such as adornment, foreplay, etc., and this is devoid of selfishness.

C - Family Dialogue:

One of the reasons for family stability is mutual dialogue among all family members, in accordance with the principles of upbringing. This avoids fanaticism, distraction from social media and avoids dialogue within the family. Furthermore, it avoids opening channels for forbidden dialogue with the opposite sex on Facebook or WhatsApp. Family dialogue is one of the reasons for the presence of affection and compassion within the family.

3. Properly Raising Children Is a Path to Social Reform:

There is no doubt that education plays a role in reforming children and advancing society. Parents must learn the scientific method of proper upbringing, as education is the primary function they must understand before having children. Otherwise, through their ignorance, they commit a grave and unforgivable sin. This is a sin against themselves, their offspring, and their society. Furthermore, they must be informed of scientific facts and foundations and utilize them as much as possible to achieve an education based on knowledge and wisdom (Yaljan, 2002, 256).

Education does not depend solely on providing for children's material needs, striving to provide them with education, attending parent-teacher meetings at schools, checking their grades, and spending time with them on holidays. Rather, it depends on building a strong family capable of facing challenges and protecting the family from corruption and harm, lest it later become a source of societal corruption. There are fundamental pillars of raising children, including the following:

A - Caring for the Child During Pregnancy:

One of the virtues of parenting is that it clarifies all the rulings related to children during pregnancy, as well as the important educational principles that result from it. This way, the parent is aware of the matter in every duty they undertake toward their children. Everyone who has the responsibility of raising their children should

fulfill their duty to the fullest, applying and implementing the foundations laid down by Islam and the principles outlined by the first educator.

There are matters that must be observed during pregnancy, namely: avoiding anything that harms the pregnancy or causes fetal deformity, such as excessive medication, medications, and radiation for the slightest reason; strenuous work; smoking by the mother or father; drugs and alcohol; and the mother should avoid being overly nervous during pregnancy. Because the mother's nervousness has a direct effect on the fetus, as the nervous system in the fetus is part of the mother's nervous system, and this is because the fetus is affected by the mother's influence (Al-Sulaiman, 2010, 17), as well as avoiding excessive sadness, all of which is prohibited in general.

B - Breastfeeding:

Physical contact is a means of conveying love. Numerous studies on child development have concluded that infants who are held, cuddled, and kissed live emotionally healthier lives than infants left for extended periods without physical contact (Chapman, 2010, 99).

Breastfeeding is the beginning of loving parenting, fulfilling all emotions, and fostering complete attachment between children and mothers. It also plants the seeds of nurturing and freeing children from psychological, physical, and mental complexes. It includes proper physical education, as there is no food comparable to breast milk. Breastfeeding is the best food for the mind, with balanced proportions that lead to optimal mental and physical development simultaneously.

C - Emotional Education:

One of the most indispensable forms of emotional education today is compassion for children. Raising children with compassion and mercy saturates a child's conscience and makes them balanced in every aspect of their lives. One of the most dangerous issues facing children during childhood is the neglect of emotional education by parents. This is more severe than hunger and thirst, because they disappear when the cause is removed. Violence, however, remains with the child, affecting them, their upbringing, and their relationship with society. Emotional education has great importance in building the child's personality and psychological safety from complexes and deviations, and instilling in him various good habits along with sound trends and desirable noble values. It would be preferable if this education were to take place within the framework of true Islamic law, which is keen on raising the child and paying attention to building his

personality in a sound manner, protecting him from all forms of deviation and types of behavioral complexes, and various dangerous psychological illnesses and ugly bad habits (Al-Khuwait, 2006, 39).

Second: The Proposed Strategy:

The proposed strategy for family reform is based on the following:

- Purifying the media of widespread violent films and scenes of murder and bloodshed that instill violence in society.
 - Providing family education in final-year curricula at all educational levels and educating students about children's rights so they can better educate themselves in the future.
 - Making family education a core subject in the educational process.
 - Focusing on each age group separately and linking these stages.
 - Educating parents on how to deal with different types of behavior (stubborn children, aggressive children, talkative children, shy children, stubborn children, inactive children, faultfinders, etc.).
 - Educating society about the causes of social deviations, their dangers, and how to prevent them.
 - Providing comprehensive care for orphans, including full integration into society and preventing isolation, while enacting laws that guarantee their rights.
- Providing exceptional care for people with disabilities, ensuring employment opportunities in the government sector upon completion of their studies. These opportunities should be compatible with their ability to work, and providing ongoing financial and moral support.
- Imposing penalties on parents for educational negligence, with parents bearing some of the legal and criminal responsibility if their child commits a criminal act before the age of puberty.
 - Enacting a law in the House of Representatives prohibiting parents from using violence against their children.
 - At the beginning of each stage of education (nursery, the first and second stages of basic education, secondary school, and university), parents should receive an educational booklet on how to successfully navigate this stage.
 - Providing parents with the latest and most advanced educational developments in the field of childrearing to facilitate their work.

-Training parents in colleges of education on proper parenting methods and building trust with their children to achieve progress, advancement, and a bright future.

-Educating children to plan well and have future goals they strive to achieve.

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